

EXPERIENCES OF NON-EDUCATION GRADUATE TEACHERS IN THE CONDUCT OF CLASSROOM OBSERVATION

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Experiences of Non- education Graduate Teachers in the Conduct of Classroom Observation

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study aims to explore the experiences of non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation. A transcendental phenomenological approach was utilized among eight non-education graduate teachers in Baybay City Senior High School who were purposively selected based on the set criteria. Transcripts of the interview were analyzed using the seven-stage Colaizzi's method of processing qualitative data. The results of the study revealed four emergent themes. First, Adaptive Pedagogical Excellence, which has three sub-themes: Exemplary Professional Dedication, Dancing through Flexibility, Reflective Harmony, and Cultivating a Positive Observation Mindset. The second theme is Exemplifying Effective and Compassionate Teaching Strategies, which has three sub-themes, namely: Cultivating a Supportive Classroom Environment, Prioritizing Students' Needs and Engagement, and Embracing Innovative and Creative Teaching Strategies. The third theme is Collaborative Professional Enhancement, which has three sub-themes: Promoting Peer Collaboration, Optimizing Observer Interaction, and Resourceful Teaching Practices. The fourth theme is Navigating Challenges in Classroom Observation, which has four sub-themes, these are Performance Stress and Burnout, Knowledge and Resource Gaps, Tackling Logistical Hurdles, and Uncharted Feedback. Based on the gathered result, it is recommended to utilize the proposed intervention to capacitate non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation that enhances their knowledge and skills in teaching pedagogies, lesson planning, and classroom management.

Keywords: *classroom observation, non-education graduate, transcendental phenomenology*

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INTRODUCTION

The advent of the K to 12 Program has become a shifting point in the education system in the Philippines. The demand for highly skilled and competent teachers who will fill the required personnel has been the key point of many to indulge in the teaching profession, including non-education graduates. The highly set standards of performance and evaluation have become an essential step to ensure quality and excellence in the teaching profession, thereby, prompting the Department of Education (DepEd) to adopt and implement the Classroom Observation Tool (COT) as a means of a standardized tool to assess and evaluate teaching performance.

On May 13, 2013, the Republic Act 10533 also known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 was passed into law and took effect on June 13, 2013. With the implementation of this law, a wider scope of learning opportunities arose, and along with it are the expectations from the teachers to deliver higher teaching performance both in content and teaching approaches that are in line with the objectives of the program. These expectations should directly be captured during their teaching performance assessment in the form of a classroom observation anchored with the more contextualized Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). RPMS has been defined by DepEd as a systemic mechanism to manage, monitor, and measure performance, and identify human resource and organizational development needs to enable continuous work improvement and individual growth (DepEd Press Release, 2018). The tool helps to ensure that teachers and administrators' performance are fairly and accurately evaluated to improve the quality of learning (Papa, 2022).

It was predominantly known that classroom observation had become part of teaching assessment that seeks to assess and provide feedback from both teachers and administrators. In fact, observations can provide a positive framework to improve one's teaching practice, enhance their pedagogical skills, and develop their teaching-learning experience (Barrogo, 2020; Caratiquit & Pablo, 2021).

The implementation of the K to 12 Program also provides many teaching opportunities as more students need to undergo an additional two years of basic education and new subjects at hand which requires specialization from competent and skillful educators, thus, more teachers are needed (Ortega et al., 2022). With this, the Government has authorized the DepEd and private secondary schools to hire non-education graduates or so-called "second coursers" to meet the demand of this program. This opportunity paved the way for many graduates and other practitioners regardless of their bachelor's degree to apply in the Department of Education.

Based on the review of the prior research, there exists a population gap in the body of knowledge. Teachers who are non-education graduates have been less explored in the context of classroom observation utilizing the RPMS-COT. Furthermore, recent studies have focused primarily on teachers' use and perception of RPMS-COT (Barrogo, 2020; Castillo, 2021 & Papa, 2022). Meanwhile, the study of Ching (2022) & Ortega et al., (2022) delves into the job satisfaction and performance level of non-education graduates and shows that these teachers have an outstanding performance in content knowledge and pedagogy, and curriculum and planning. Furthermore, Wong (2020) explored the teaching competence and attitude towards the teaching profession of non-education graduate teachers as compared to education graduates. Although these studies offer insights into the performance of non-education graduate teachers, it remains apparent that a more in-depth exploration of their lived experiences during classroom observation is warranted. This study can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of their teaching performance.

In Baybay City Senior High School (BCSHS), where this study was conducted, more than half of the total population of the teaching force are non-education graduates who possess the knowledge and expertise to teach the different complex and advanced subjects as stipulated under the new curriculum. BCSHS teachers regardless of their educational background need to undergo four observations in the entire duration of the School Year, one observation per quarter. Each teacher is expected to prepare and deliver the best quality teaching performance that should hit the target indicators stipulated in the Classroom Observation Tool (COT).

With the use of the RPMS-COT which assesses and expects all public-school teachers to deliver the utmost quality in the teaching-learning process regardless of the educational background acquired by the teacher, it poses a question to wonder how these second coursers prepare themselves to achieve what is expected from them in the classroom setting. Thus, this study was conceptualized.

Research Questions

Baybay City Senior High School has a total population of 101 teaching personnel, 72 of whom or 71% are non-education graduate teachers who will undergo four (4) classroom observations every School Year. The Humanities and Social Sciences Department, in particular, consists of 25 highly skilled teachers who are experts in their field of study. More than half (52%) or 13 teachers of its total teaching personnel are non-education graduates who are identified as participants of this study. Thus, there is a need to investigate the lived experiences of these non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation who come from different fields of study and whose background and experience are limited in teaching pedagogies and classroom management.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study is a qualitative research approach using the Transcendental Phenomenological design contributed by Husserl (1859-1938) as it described the experiences of non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation. Since this study aimed to explore the lived experiences of teachers, a transcendental phenomenology to describe the experiences of the participants in a more systematic, objective, and meaningful approach.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Baybay City Senior High School located at 30 de Diciembre St., City of Baybay. It is a stand-alone school that was established in 2016 during the first implementation of the Grade 12 program. Baybay City Senior High School offers different tracks such as the Academic track, Arts and Design track, and Technical Vocational and Livelihood track. The academic track is composed of STEM, ABM, GA, and HUMSS. Moreover, the school has an estimated number of 2300 enrollees for the school year 2023-2024.

The Humanities and Social Sciences Department is currently considered as the largest department in the school which comprises 25 strong teaching personnel. Among these 25-teaching staff, more than half (52%) or 13 teachers are non-education graduates who will serve as participants of this study. The said teachers who are non-education graduates will undergo classroom observation every quarter of the entire School Year, hence four Classroom observations.

Research Instrument

To acquire sufficient and valuable data from the participants' experiences in classroom observation, the study utilized an interview schedule to capture all relevant responses during the interview session. Likewise, an audio recording was also used upon the consent of the participants to get the responses in detail and making sure that no information was left behind, this is found in the consent letter delivered to them prior to the conduct of the interview. I also used field notes to list down important information which also helped me during the interview as I could glean interesting responses which I raised for further clarification. During the interview, I utilized a semi-structured approach with an open-ended question to disclose participants' actual experiences on classroom observation in the senior high school. This method of interview will give the interviewer the freedom to slightly diverge from the script allowing for a deeper understanding of the subject depending on how the conversation progressed (McIntosh & Morse, 2015). The semi-structured interview follows a framework that identifies pre-determined primary questions or major topics and is followed by sub-topics or "probes" that the interviewer will use throughout the interview (Heigham & Croker, 2008; Pathak & Intratat, 2012).

Data Gathering

To gather substantial data on this study, I employed a step-by-step procedure which was categorized into three phases, namely: preliminary activities, main activities, and post activities.

The preliminary activities involved the crafting and sending of transmittal and consent letters as well as the scheduling of the interview. First, I sent a letter of permission to the Dean of Graduate School to allow the conduct of the study. Second, once the letter was approved, I sent a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) to conduct the research in Baybay City Senior High School, Baybay City Division. Third, after the approval of the Division Superintendent, I sent a letter to the School Head of Baybay City Senior High School to allow the conduct of this study at the said institution. Fourth, upon the approval of the letter by the School Head, I immediately sent a consent letter to the participants who first agreed to have an interview during the preliminary survey. Then, the scheduling of the interview was done on the desired date and venue.

The main activities include my actual gathering of data through face-to-face and one-on-one interviews with the selected participants. I conducted the interview mostly in the participants' advisory room during their vacant time without the presence of the students, this is to make sure that the environment is a conducive place where only me and the participant is present to allow the participant to freely express his/her experience. I also made sure that the interview

was conducted not within class hours so as not to compromise the time of the interview. Most of the interview falls on Wednesdays as most of the participants have no class schedule during this day. Furthermore, during the conduct of the interview, the institution allotted Wednesday as Organization Day and/or other school-related activities (if any), thus, most teachers are vacant on this day and only a few classes are recited. There was a minimum of 38 minutes and a maximum of one-hour duration of the interview. As the interviewer, I personally manage the flow of the interview process.

The post-activities include the actual events after the interview. This includes an informal conversation with the participant about what had transpired in the interview. I then gave a token of my appreciation to my participants. There was a debriefing with the participants after the interview, the debriefing includes re-assuring the participants' responses and personal data are kept confidential and will only be used for the purpose of the research. Likewise, I have stated the purpose of my study and that all data gathered will only be used as a contribution to the body of knowledge. Then, I checked my audio recording if the quality was good enough for me to analyze the data. The recorded responses were then transcribed, analyzed, and interpreted personally before it was put into writing. To ensure the validity of the data, the significant statements extracted along with the themes and sub-themes were presented to the participants. With this, it provided an avenue for them to ask questions and clarifications and were addressed appropriately.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After a thorough analysis of the data gathered, there are Four emergent themes that reflect the experiences of the non-education graduate teachers. First, Adaptive Pedagogical Excellence, which has three sub-themes such as Exemplary Professional Dedication, Dancing through Flexibility, Reflective Harmony, and Cultivating a Positive Observation Mindset. The second theme is Exemplifying Effective and Compassionate Teaching Strategies, which has three sub-themes, namely: Cultivating a Supportive Classroom Environment, prioritizing Students' Needs and Engagement, and Embracing Innovative and Creative Teaching Strategies.

The third theme is Collaborative Professional Enhancement, which has three sub-themes which are Promoting Peer Collaboration, Optimizing Observer Interaction, and Resourceful Teaching Practices. The fourth theme is Navigating Challenges in Classroom Observation, which has four sub-themes, these are: Performance Stress and Burnout, Knowledge and Resource Gaps, Tackling Logistical Hurdles, and Uncharted Feedback.

Adaptive Pedagogical Excellence

This is the first theme of the experiences of the non-education graduate teachers, the theme consists of four sub-themes, Exemplary Professional Dedication, Dancing through Flexibility, Reflective Harmony, and Cultivating a Positive Observation Mindset. This theme mainly describes the experiences of the participants who are adaptive to their current situation, especially during a classroom observation. This adaptive concept manifests the non-education graduate teachers who are dedicated to pursue excellence in their current profession, who are able to dance with the different waves of the situation at hand and are able to cope and find

tangible solutions to every arising challenge, particularly in the conduct of classroom observation. Likewise, non-education graduate teachers embody a positive attitude towards observation, considering this not merely as an evaluative process but a valuable opportunity to improve their teaching skills which ultimately leads to excellence in their profession.

Figure 1. Adaptive Pedagogical Excellence experienced by non-education graduate teachers

Exemplifying Effective and Compassionate Teaching Strategies

This is the second theme covering the sub-theme Cultivating a Supportive Classroom Environment, Prioritizing Students' Needs and Engagement, and Embracing Innovative and Creative Teaching Strategies. This theme represents the participants' experiences in employing different teaching strategies during the conduct of classroom observation. It entails classroom management and creating a positive learning environment to the learners, additionally, it encompasses their ability to teach authentic learning to the learners and likewise implements innovative and creative strategies to address and sustain the learning preferences of the diverse learners.

Teaching strategies focusing on student-centered is an essential aspect during classroom observation. It deliberately shows the ability of the teacher to implement the lesson with diverse strategies with respect to the learners' learning styles and at the same time create a conducive atmosphere where students can actively participate without the fear of being embarrassed.

Figure 2. Exemplifying Effective and Compassionate Teaching Strategies among non-education graduate teachers

Collaborative Professional Enhancement

This is the third theme that centers on the experiences of non-education graduate teachers as they continuously seek technical assistance and advice from both peers and observers. This collaborative effort enhances their performance in the conduct of classroom observation and improves their teaching skills. Furthermore, it sheds light on how participants leverage various resources to effectively deliver their lessons during observations.

Non-education graduates having been into different professional fields heavily relied on peer collaboration as an avenue for them to learn the process of classroom observation and at the same time seek appropriate methodologies to be implemented. The theme also describes the role of the observer as a technical advisor to better improve the performance of the participant's teaching skills. Additionally, it underscores the collaborative and resourceful nature of participants with the utilization of a diverse range of learning materials and tools for continuous improvement in the teaching process. The theme encompasses three sub-themes, Promoting Peer Collaboration, Optimizing Observer Interaction, and Resourceful Teaching Practices.

Figure 3. Collaborative Professional Enhancement experienced by non-education graduate teachers

Navigating Challenges in Classroom Observation

This is the fourth theme covering the sub-themes Performance Stress and Burnout, Knowledge and Resource Gaps, Tackling Logistical Hurdles, and Uncharted Reflection. This theme encompasses the different challenges experienced by non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of Classroom Observation. Being a non-graduate in the field of education, participants have undeniably encountered various challenges throughout the process of the observation, which in any way have also been a platform for improvement and a reflective avenue for some.

These challenges encompass the anxiety they have experienced before, during, and after the observation, likewise, it also includes the limited knowledge in the observation process, limitation of resources as well as the difficulty in crafting the Lesson Plan for observation. In addition, participants also experienced either a delay or no post-observation conducted which consequently affected the improvement process of the teacher. Interestingly, however, participants have somehow coped with these challenges and use these as a means of motivation to further seek ways to improve their teaching process.

Figure 4. Navigating challenges experienced during classroom observation

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

After a thorough analysis of the data gathered, there are Four emergent themes that reflect the experiences of the non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation. First, Adaptive Pedagogical Excellence, which has three sub-themes such as Exemplary Professional Dedication, Dancing through Flexibility, Reflective Harmony, and Cultivating a Positive Observation Mindset. The second theme is Exemplifying Effective and Compassionate Teaching Strategies, which has three sub-themes, namely: Cultivating a Supportive Classroom Environment, Prioritizing Students' Needs and Engagement, and Embracing Innovative and Creative Teaching Strategies. The third theme is Collaborative Professional Enhancement, which has three sub-themes which are Promoting Peer Collaboration, Optimizing Observer Interaction, and Resourceful Teaching Practices. The fourth theme is Navigating Challenges in Classroom Observation, which has four sub-themes, these are: Performance Stress and Burnout, Knowledge and Resource Gaps, Tackling Logistical Hurdles, and Uncharted Feedback.

Conclusion

Results gathered from the experiences of non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation concluded that these experiences exerted a profound and comprehensive influence on the participants' personal, professional, and emotional well-being as a teacher both positively and negatively. It is concluded that there is a need to fill the gap in knowledge of different pedagogies specific to the learning objectives is extremely important to capacitate non-education graduate teachers to become more effective educators. Likewise, participants had experienced difficulty in the crafting of the Lesson Plan which is equally important to ensure coherent and well-structured delivery of the lesson. It was also revealed that there are no enough learning materials in the senior high school which is more content-wise to be utilized by most of the teachers. Non-education graduate teachers also need to resolve their personal struggles such as anxiety, self-doubt, and uneasiness towards the observation. Lastly, participants had experienced the absence of a post-observation conference which should be religiously conducted to all teachers who have undergone classroom observation not just to evaluate themselves but also to glean valuable insights for ongoing improvement, Given the result of this study, it is concluded further that there is a need to capacitate non-education graduate teachers in the conduct of classroom observation with respect to the challenges they have encountered.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were drawn based on the findings and conclusion of the study:

1. Capacitate teachers on different teaching pedagogies aligned to their subject area through seminars, In-Service Education and Training (INSET), and School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) sessions.

2. Integrate lesson planning sessions as part of the orientation for the newly hired and non-education graduate teachers at the start of the school year.
3. Innovate locally-made and quality-assured learning materials to compensate for the lack of learning resources in senior high school.
4. Engage teachers in a series of Psychosocial activities throughout the year such as mindfulness and relaxation techniques, and emotional regulation workshops which can help them manage their personal struggles related to classroom observation.
5. Encourage school heads, department heads, and master teachers who act as observers to religiously conduct post-observation conferences right after the observation schedule.
6. Conduct further study in the field of non-education graduate teachers.

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